

MISMANAGEMENT OF PRIMARY EDUCATION SYSTEM IN INDIA – ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS RESPONSIBLE FACTORS AND THE POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

Primary education or elementary education is the first stage of compulsory education prior to the secondary education. It is this stage wherein the pure minds are ready to be blended and molded in such a way that they can be converted into the individuals on whom the responsibilities of making their society and nation proud can be shouldered. Constitution of India comprises of various articles which prescribes that the free and compulsory education is the fundamental right of each and every children between the age group of 6 and 14 years. Education to the pupil is provided by the public sector schools and the private sector schools. Ratio of public schools to private schools in India is 7:5. Controlling and funding of these schools takes place under three levels: central, state and local.

As far as primary education is concerned, India has made the significant progress in increasing the attendance rate and expanding literacy to approximately three quarters of the population in the 7-10 age group by 2011. Many research scholars and governmental and non-governmental bodies consider that the improved education system in India would be the main contributor to its economic development. But on the contrary to all the claims that the authority makes, primary education system in India faces many challenges and problems. The Indian government lays emphasis on primary education for the children aged between 6 – 14 years. The Indian government has also banned child labour so that instead of working under the unsafe condition, children can go to school. However, because of the economic disparity and social conditions, both free education and ban on child labour are difficult to enforce. Primary education system, because of shortage of resources and lack of political wills, suffers from massive loopholes such as high pupil to teacher ratios, shortage of infrastructure, poor levels of teacher training, improper teaching and learning environment, lack of motivation for both the students and the teachers, improper management, etc.

The main aim of this research paper is to discuss in detail the various parameters responsible for the mismanagement of the primary education system in India, analyse these factors and to suggest the various solutions to overcome this problem of mismanagement of primary education by taking broad parameters into consideration.

Keywords: *primary education system, Learning environment, Loopholes from the society and Government.*

Introduction

In ancient times, India had the Gurukul system of education in which anyone who wished to study went to a teacher's (Guru) house and requested to be taught. In this system, all learning was closely linked to nature and to life, and not confined to memorizing some information. The modern school system was brought to India, including the English language, originally by Lord Thomas Babington Macaulay in the 1830s. Teaching was confined to classrooms and the link with nature was broken.

Primary education is the first step in the life of a student with which he/she starts his/her career. Hence, it is very important for the parents and the bodies governing the education system to put an extra care at this stage as this particular stage not only set up a stepping stone for the development of the student but also for the development of the economy of the country.

Enhancing quality in education therefore must be based on developing educational systems that are integrative and responsive to the multiple obstacles to the children's learning. Enhancing quality in the education reduces gender and other inequalities, improves children's health and

nutrition, addresses issue related to the parental and community involvement and the management of the educational system itself.

Table below shows the number of schools during a particular session

SR. NO.	YEAR	NUMBER OF SCHOOLS
1	2002-2003	8,53,601
2	2006-2007	11,96,663
3	2007-2008	12,50,775
4	2008-2009	12,85,576
5	2013-2014	12,91,719
6	2015-2016	1.3 million

TABLE 1. Session wise increase in number of schools

Table1 shows that there has been a consistent increase in the number of schools over a period of time. However, many of the schools fail to provide the basic facilities required for the fruitful learning and the successful completion of the course.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In recent decades India has made significant progress on access to schooling and enrollment rates in primary education but dropout rates and low levels of learning remain challenges for the state and central government.

Primary school enrollment in India has been a success story, largely due to various programs and drives to increase enrolment even in remote areas. With enrollment reaching at least 96 percent since 2009, and girls making up 56 percent of new students between 2007 and 2015, it is clear that many problems of access to schooling have been addressed. Improvements to infrastructure have been a priority to achieve this and India now has 1.4 million schools and 7.7 million teachers so that 98 percent of habitations have a primary school (class I-V) within one kilometer and 92 percent have an upper primary school (class VI-VIII) within a three-kilometer walking distance.

Despite these improvements, keeping children in school through graduation is still an issue and dropout rates continue to be high. Nationally 29 percent of children drop out before completing five years of primary school, and 43 percent before finishing upper primary school. This lands India among the top five nations for out-of-school children of primary school age, with 1.4 million 6 to 11 year olds not attending school. In many ways schools are not equipped to handle the full population – there is a teacher shortage of 689,000 teachers in primary schools, only 53 percent of schools have functional girls’ toilets and 74 percent have access to drinking water.

Additionally, the quality of learning is a major issue and reports show that children are not achieving class-appropriate learning levels. According to Pratham’s Annual Status of Education 2013 report, close to 78 percent of children in Standard III and about 50 percent of children in Standard V cannot yet read Standard II texts. Without immediate and urgent help, these children cannot effectively progress in the education system, and so improving the quality of learning in schools is the next big challenge for both the state and central governments.

Improving learning will require attention to many things, including increasing teacher accountability. According to school visits teacher attendance is just 85 percent in primary and middle schools and raising the amount of time teachers spend on-task and increasing their responsibility for student learning also needs improvement. Part of this process requires better assessments at each grade level and more efficient monitoring and support systems.

Most Indian schools have a strong focus on academic subjects, with little scope for creativity and few or no extra-curricular activities. Traditional schooling methods tend to emphasize learning without understanding the basics and the concepts and memorisation, rather than encouraging independent or creative thinking.

Overall, the primary education system needs a better general management system.

Methodology

In order to find out and analyse the various factors responsible for the mismanagement of the primary education system, we will be considering primary sources and the secondary sources of the data.

Primary data is that data which is collected on a real time basis directly from the concerned entity or the individual through various data collection and survey tools such as the questionnaires, interviews, observations, etc. whereas the secondary data is the already available data with the website of the concerned entity or with the governing organisation for the entity or from the published data like in research journals, newspapers, magazines, etc.

In our research study, the primary data is collected by means of the three tools of survey.

- 1) **Questionnaire** – Data is collected from the parents of the students by providing them the questionnaire in the objective form.
- 2) **Interviews** – Data is collected by taking the interviews of the candidate, parents, teachers, non-teaching staff and the management of the school.
- 3) **Observations** – Data is collected by observing the overall functioning of several sample schools.

Secondary data is collected through the websites of the schools and through the websites of the governing body for the management of the schools in India.

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR MISMANAGEMENT

For this research, in order to find out the various responsible factors for the mismanagement of primary education system in India, operation of 56 schools was analysed collectively with the help of questionnaire, observation and interviews. From 56 schools, which included 16 public schools, 29 private schools and 11 Zillah Parishad schools, total of 322 questionnaires were collected from the parents of the students. Total 221 teachers of the schools were interviewed..

While carrying out this research, three types of schools were taken into consideration:

1. Public schools
2. Private schools
3. Zillah Parishad schools

Two types of courses that were taken into consideration for the study includes:

1. State Board Education
2. CBSE

Factors; taken into the study which is considered to be responsible for the mismanagement of primary education system includes:

A] Factors responsible for the student dropouts:

1. Poor academic performance
2. Economic problems of the family
3. Lack of student and parent engagement
4. Students are required to work while carrying out education.

B] Factors reducing importance of education among the students

1. Lack of vision among the students and improper guidance from the teachers
2. Parents showing little interest for the education of the student.
3. More involvement of parents in the extracurricular activities rather than the students themselves.

C] Factors that make learning environment pathetic

1. Lack of safety in the environment and unavailability of health care means
2. Environment of the city and lack of easy access to transportation
3. Improper school design and lack of physical facilities such as water, toilets, classrooms, seating arrangements, etc.

D] Social factors which makes the learning environment difficult

1. Lack of encouragement from friends and family
2. Negative attitude of the society towards education

E] Miscellaneous factors that result into the mismanagement of primary education system in India.

Low qualification and lack of motivation of the teacher results into the mismanagement of primary education system.

1. Bad teacher to student relationship, failure to teach with clarity and lack of computer and library facilities results into the mismanagement of primary education system.
2. Lack of seriousness for examination by student, parents and teachers and lack of attention of the management and the governing body of the school towards the development of the education system results into the mismanagement of primary education system.

Analysis of the Factors and Findings

Survey data were plotted on the bar charts. Depending on the response, various factors were analysed and the results were interpreted.

Graph 1 shows that out of the chosen 56 schools for the sample space, 34 schools were located in the rural area and 22 schools were located in the urban area.

GRAPH 1: Location of the sample school

Graph 2.1 shows that out of the total 322 questionnaires collected from the parents of the students, 187 numbers of parents belonged to rural area and 135 belonged to urban area

GRAPH 2.1: Location wise number of parents.

Graph 2.2 shows that out of the total 221 teachers being interviewed across different districts, 96 numbers of teachers belonged to rural area and 125 belonged to urban area.

GRAPH 2.2: Location wise number of interviewed teachers
Class wise distribution of students

RURAL AREA

GRAPH 3.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 3.2

Graph 3.1 shows that out of the total 187 student samples from the rural area, 31 students are studying in kindergarten to standard 1 level, 48 are studying in standard 2 level, 49 are studying in standard 3 level and 59 are studying in standard 4 level.

Graph 3.2 shows that out of the total 135 student samples from the urban area, 21 students are studying in kindergarten to standard 1 level, 32 are studying in standard 2 level, 37 are studying in standard 3 level and 45 are studying in standard 4 level.

Distribution according to the board of study

RURAL AREA

GRAPH4.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 4.2

Graph 4.1 shows that out of 187 sample students from the rural area, 76.47% of students are studying under the state board pattern and 23.53% of students are studying under CBSE course pattern.

Graph 4.2 shows that out of 135 sample students from the urban area, 42.96% of students are studying under the state board pattern and 57.04% of students are studying under CBSE course pattern.

Students studying in different types of schools

RURAL AREA

GRAPH 5.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 5.2

Graph 5.1 shows that out of 187 sample students from the rural areas, 33.16% of students are enrolled with the public school, 25.67% are enrolled with the private school and 41.18% of students are enrolled with the Zillah Parishad School.

Graph 5.2 shows that out of 135 sample students from the urban areas, 31.85% of students are enrolled with the public school, 48.89% are enrolled with the private school and 19.26% of students are enrolled with the Zillah Parishad School.

Working status of the parents.

GRAPH 6.1

GRAPH 6.2

Graph 6.1 shows that out of 187 sample students from the rural area, 36.37% of students have only father among the parents who is working, 11.23% of students have only mother among the parents who is working and 52.41% of students are such that both their father and mother are working.

Graph 6.2 shows that out of 135 sample students from the urban area, 43.7% of students have only father among the parents who is working, 19.26% of students have only mother among the parents who is working and 37.04% of students are such that both their father and mother are working.

Working status of the students

GRAPH: 7.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 7.2

Graph 7.1 shows that out of 187 sample students from the rural area, 78.08% of students are working along with carrying out their primary education. Out of the working students, 19.18% of students are in second standard, 33.56% of students are in third standard and 47.26% of students are in fourth standard. 21.93% of students are not working.

Graph 7.2 shows that out of 135 sample students from the urban area, 17.04% of students are working along with carrying out their primary education. Out of the working students, 30.44% students are in third standard and 69.57% of students are in fourth standard. 82.96% of students are not working.

Distribution of the qualification of parents.

GRAPH 8.1

GRAPH 8.2

Graph 8.1 shows that out of 187 sample students from the rural area, 28.88% of students have their parents who are only qualified till SSC, 25.67% of students have their parents who are only qualified till HSSC, 10.16% of students have their parents who are qualified till graduation, 4.81% of students have their parents who are qualified till post-graduation and 30.48% of students have their parents who are illiterate.

Graph 8.2 shows that out of 135 sample students from the urban area, 6.67% of students have their parents who are only qualified till SSC, 8.15% of students have their parents who are only qualified till HSSC, 45.93% of students have their parents who are qualified till graduation, 36.3% of students have their parents who are qualified till post-graduation and only 2.96% of students have their parents who are illiterate.

GENERAL FINDINGS

A] Factors responsible for student dropouts

1. Poor academic performance
 2. Economic problems of the family
 3. Lack of student and parent engagement
 4. Students are required to work while carrying out education.
- Are some of the factor which results into student dropout**

RURAL AREA

GRAPH 9.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 9.2

Graph 9.1 shows that out of 187 parents of the students from the rural areas, 38.51% of parents strongly feels that poor academic performance, economic problems of the family, lack of student and parent engagement and the requirement of students to work while carrying out education are some of the factors which results into student dropout, 27.27% also agree with the same opinion, 19.79% feels that it somehow affects the dropout rates while 9.63% disagree and 4.81% of parents strongly feels that the above said factors seldom play any role for student dropout.

Graph 9.2 shows that out of 135 parents of the students from the urban areas, 45.19% of parents strongly feels that poor academic performance, economic problems of the family, lack of student and parent engagement and the requirement of students to work while carrying out education are some of the factors which results into student dropout, 25.93% also agree with the same opinion, 14.08% feels that it somehow affects the dropout rates while 13.34% disagree and 1.48% strongly feels that the above said factors seldom play any role for student dropout.

B] Factors reducing importance of education among the students

1. Lack of vision among the students and improper guidance from the teachers
2. Parents showing little interest for the education of the student.
3. More involvement of parents in the extracurricular activities rather than the students themselves

Are some of the factors which results into the reduction of the importance of education among the students.

RURAL AREA

GRAPH 10.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 10.2

Graph 10.1 shows that out of 187 parents of the students from the rural areas, 31.01% of the parents strongly feels that the lack of vision among the students and improper guidance from the teachers, parents showing little interest for the education of the student and more involvement of parents in the extracurricular activities rather than the students themselves results into the reduction of the importance of education among the students, 56.15% also agree with the same opinion, 11.77% feels that it somehow reduces the importance of education among the students, while 1.07% of the parents disagree with the opinion that the above said factors seldom play any role for the reduction of importance of education among the students.

Graph 10.2 shows that out of 135 parents of the students from the urban areas, 91.11% of the parents strongly feels that the lack of vision among the students and improper guidance from the teachers, parents showing little interest for the education of the student and more involvement of parents in the extracurricular activities rather than the students themselves results into the reduction of the importance of education among the students, 7.41% also agree with the same opinion while 1.48% of the parents feels that it somehow reduces the importance of education among the students

C] Factors that make learning environment pathetic

1. Lack of safety in the environment and unavailability of health care means
2. Environment of the city and lack of easy access to transportation.
3. Improper school design and lack of physical facilities such as water, toilets, classrooms, seating arrangement, etc.

Are some of the factors that make the learning environment pathetic.

RURAL AREA

GRAPH 11.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 11.2

Graph 11.1 shows that out of 187 parents of the students from the rural areas, 60.43% of the parents strongly feels that lack of safety in the environment and unavailability of health care means, environment of the city and lack of easy access to transportation and Improper school design and lack of physical facilities such as water, toilets, classrooms, seating arrangement, etc are some of the factors that makes the learning environment pathetic, 37.97% also agree with the same opinion while 1.61% of the parents feels that it somehow makes the learning environment pathetic.

Graph 11.2 shows that out of 135 parents of the students from the urban areas, 89.63% of the parents strongly feels that lack of safety in the environment and unavailability of health care means, environment of the city and lack of easy access to transportation and Improper school design and lack of physical facilities such as water, toilets, classrooms, seating arrangement, etc are some of the factors that makes the learning environment pathetic, 8.89% also agree with the same opinion while 1.48% of the parents feels that it somehow makes the learning environment pathetic.

D] Social factors which makes the learning environment difficult

1. Lack of encouragement from friends and family
2. Negative attitude of the society towards education

Are the Social factors which make the learning environment difficult.

RURAL AREA

GRAPH 12.1

URBAN AREA

GRAPH 12.2

Graph 12.1 shows that out of 96 teachers who were interviewed in the school of the rural areas, 37.5% of the teachers strongly feels that the lack of encouragement from friends and family and the negative attitude of the society towards education are the Social factors which make the learning environment difficult. 44.8% also agree with the same opinion, 13.57% of the teachers feels that it somehow reduces the importance of education among the students while 2.1% of the teachers disagree with the opinion and 2.1% of the teachers strongly feels that these factors makes the learning environment difficult.

Graph 12.2 shows that out of 125 teachers who were interviewed in the school of the urban areas, 28% of the teachers strongly feels that the lack of encouragement from friends and family and the negative attitude of the society towards education are the social factors makes the learning environment difficult, 60.8% also agree with the same opinion, 4% of the teachers feels that it somehow makes the learning environment difficult while 2.4% of the teachers disagree with the opinion and 4.8% of the teachers strongly feels that these factors makes the learning environment difficult.

E] Miscellaneous factors that result into the mismanagement of primary education system.

1. Low qualification and lack of motivation of the teacher results into the mismanagement of primary education system.
2. Bad teacher to student relationship, failure to teach with clarity and lack of computer and library facilities results into the mismanagement of primary education system.
3. Lack of seriousness for examination by student, parents and teachers and lack of attention of the management and the governing body of the school towards the development of the education system results into the mismanagement of primary education system.

Are some of the miscellaneous factors that result into the mismanagement of primary education system.

GRAPH 13.1

GRAPH 13.2

Graph 13.1 shows that out of 187 parents of the students from the rural areas, 47.6% of the parents strongly feels that low qualification and lack of motivation of the teacher, bad teacher to student relationship, failure to teach with clarity and lack of computer and library facilities, lack of seriousness for examination by student, parents and teachers and lack of attention of the management and the governing body of the school towards the development of the education system results into the mismanagement of primary education system. 49.2% also agree with the same opinion while 3.21% of the parents feels that the above said factors somehow results into the mismanagement of primary education system.

Graph 13.2 shows that out of 135 parents of the students from the urban areas, 68.89% of the parents strongly feels that low qualification and lack of motivation of the teacher, bad teacher to student relationship, failure to teach with clarity and lack of computer and library facilities, lack of seriousness for examination by student, parents and teachers and lack of attention of the management and the governing body of the school towards the development of the education system results into the mismanagement of primary education system. 23.71% also agree with the same opinion while 7.41% of the parents feels that it somehow results into the mismanagement of primary education system.

Suggestions for the Remedy

All the factors which are studied above are interrelated with each other and hence an overall improvement is required for the successful management of the primary education system in India. First of all a good infrastructure has to be created so as to bring about an enthusiasm among the students. Physical facilities such as availability of pure drinking water, hygienic mid-day meals, availability of separate washrooms for boys and girls, etc. has to be maintained which would create a good learning environment. Transportation facilities should be made available by the school authority for the students. Government provides special concession for the students using the public transport system. Government has also made several amendments for the safety of the students using school bus.

Environment in which the school is operating should be made safe and necessary health care means should be maintained by the school authority to make the learning environment conducive. Tree plantation, regular cleaning of the school premises, maintaining the first aid kits and appointment of a personal doctor for the school can solve the issue.

Governing body of the school should appoint well qualified teachers having enough competencies to teach the students with clarity. Proper teacher to student ration is also very necessary for useful learning. Generally, there should be a teacher for around 35 students. While appointing new teachers, demonstration should be taken in front of the students by the management of the school so as to analyse the ability and clarity with which the teacher can teach. Training and development session should plan annually for the teachers so that they can address the problems of the students.

Many a time teachers provide such a home assignment to the students which they can hardly do when their age and ability is taken into consideration. Moreover only one to two days of deadline is provided by the teachers to the students for completing the assignment. Under such situation, it is the parents who completes the assignments of the students at home be it an academic work or an extracurricular activity. This, instead of developing the students, brings about a kind of an attitude in him of getting completed their works by somebody else. Hence, teachers should provide assignments according to the ability of the student with the adequate time to complete it. School authority should conduct several seminars in a month for the parents and the teachers wherein the experts should be guiding them with the schemes of the government for the education of the children. Parents should be made aware that they should not send their children for work as it would hamper the future growth of their children. Parents should be given knowledge about the various scopes of education and the benefits of the education for their child. Parents and teachers should be encouraged to provide special attention for those students who are not doing well with their academics. Updated library and computer facility should also be made available for the students.

It is the duty of the government to improve the education system by introducing new schemes for the development of the education system and by implementing the previously introduced schemes. It is the duty of the management to keep their schools updated with all the necessary facilities required for the enthusiastic learning environment. It is the duty of the teachers to personally take the problems of the students and try to eradicate them out. Finally, it is the duty

of the parents to get involved into the education of their children personally and to focus only on the education of their ward so that they can make them proud.

Conclusion

Primary education system could be managed properly if all the associated entities get involved in it positively. Government of India has introduced several schemes for the development of the elementary education system. These schemes include:

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan :SSA has been operational since 2000-2001 to provide for a variety of interventions for universal access and retention, bridging of gender and social category gaps in elementary education and improving the quality of learning.

Mid-Day Meal Scheme: With a view to enhancing enrolment, retention and attendance and simultaneously improving nutritional levels among children, the National Program of Nutritional Support to Primary Education (NP-NSPE) was launched as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme on 15th August 1995.

Strengthening of Teacher's Training Institutes: Originally, the Government launched the Scheme of Restructuring and Re-organisation of Teacher Education in 1987. The aim of this scheme was to create a sound institutional infrastructure for pre-service and in-service training of elementary and secondary school teachers and for provision of academic resource support to elementary and secondary schools.

Scheme for Infrastructure Development in Minority Institutes (IDMI): IDMI has been operationalized to augment Infrastructure in Private Aided/Unaided Minority Schools/Institutions in order to enhance quality of education to minority children.

Mahila Samakhya Program: The National Policy on Education, 1986 recognised that the empowerment of women is possibly the most critical pre-condition for the participation of girls and women in the educational process. The Mahila Samakhya program was launched in 1988 to pursue the objectives of the National Policy on Education, 1986. It recognised that education can be an effective tool for women's empowerment

Scheme to Provide Quality Education in Madrasas (SPQEM): SPQEM seeks to bring about qualitative improvement in Madrasas to enable Muslim children attain standards of the national education system in formal education subjects.

Implementation of all the above listed schemes and the suggestions discussed earlier, management of the school, teachers and parents of the students can effectively manage the primary education system.

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